

Disease resistance

Reaction to blast (BI) and brown planthopper (BPH) of promising rice varieties for Cuu Long Delta

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BI and BPH are constraints to rice production in Cuu Long Delta. Different physiological races of the BI pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. have been found at different locations in the rice growing area. We tested many rice varieties at 3 sites in standard BI nurseries in 1981-83. BPH resistance was studied in the greenhouse using the IRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Results are in Table 1. The reaction of a few local varieties was tested during 1983 *he thu* season (Table 2). □

Table 1. Reaction of rice varieties to BI and BPH.

Variety	Duration (d)	BI			BPH
		An Giang	Hau Giang	Tien Giang	
IR2171742-1	95	2	1	3	3
BG367-7	95	2	2	0	3
IR19735-5-2-3-2	98	2	3	3	3
IR13240-10-1	115	3	3	3	1
IR13240-108-2-2-3	115	1	1	0	3
IR1820-52-24-1	125	2	1	1	1
IR1820-210-2	125	1	1	1	5
IR4547-61-3	125	1	1	1	5
IR13429-109-2-2-1 (IR56)	105	1	1	2	Not yet tested
IR13240-53-6	110	2	2	2	—
IR9852-93-2-2-2-3	140	2	1	3	5
IR48 (NN 5B), resistant check	130	1	1	1	5
IR9224-117-2-3-3-1 (IR50)	100	—	8	—	—
IR2307-247-2-2-3 (NN 6A)	115	—	8	—	—
IR9129-192-2-3-5 (NN 7A)	95	—	—	9	—

Table 2. Reaction of local varieties to BI. Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam.

Variety	Duration (d)	Reaction to BI		
		An Giang	Hau Giang	Tien Giang
Te tep	115	2	1	1
Bau quang Phu Tho	115	2	1	1
Bau Thanh Hon	115	1	2	1
Chah Phu Tho	115	2	2	1
Sai Duong Thai Nguyen	115	2	2	1
Di Huong Hai Phong	120	2	2	3

Insect resistance

Rice varieties resistant to gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae*

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GM attacks rice from seedling stage to panicle initiation and causes crop losses in the Low Country Wet Zone, especially from Apr to Aug. We evaluated experimental lines for GM resistance in 1981-83.

Three-wk-old seedlings were transplanted in 20 hills with 3 rows per test variety at 20- × 7.5-cm spacing in 3 replications. Resistant BG400-1/BW 266-7 and susceptible BG94-1 were planted at regular intervals. Recom-

Promising GM-resistant varieties^a after 3 yr of screening at Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Variety ^b	Cross	Donor parent	1981	1982	1983
BW293-1	IR2071-586/BG400-1	BG400-1	HR	HR	HR
BW288-2	BG90-2/BG400-1	BG400-1	HR	—	MR
BW293-2	IR2071-586/BG400-1		HR	HR	R
BW295-5	OB678/BW254-1	OB678	HR	HR	R
BW288-1	OB678/BW254-1	OB678	MR	MR	MR
BW288-1	BG90-2/BG400-1	—	S	S	—
BW271-1	BG259-4BW 100	—	S	S	MS

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible. ^bBW = Bombuwela, 200 series = cross number, and last number = selection.

mended fertilization and weeding were practiced. Test varieties were scored 8 wk after transplanting when the susceptible check had severe infestation (about 40% galls). Galls and tillers/hill were counted, and resistance was rated by the Standard Evaluation System for

Rice. About 30 varieties were screened every season. The most promising ones are given in the table.

The source of GM resistance in all the varieties in the table is OB678 or BG400, a line derived from OB678//IR20/H4. □